

ISic0805

Fragmentary latin inscription mentioning a proconsul

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble (pink)

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 9 September 1970, on the pavement near the entrance to room 2 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.998054, 14.262639

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20228

Physical Description

A fragment of a pinkish marble slab, chiselled on the rear. Part of the right margin is preserved, but the stone is broken on all other sides.

Dimensions

Height 26 cm

Width 31 cm

Depth 4-4.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters are 50mm high, tall, thin, serifed. P and R are open; the hastae of M join early and extend upwards; a hedera like interpunct (tail top and bottom to a hollow element) appears once between C and V of line 2.

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 50 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]idi o []
2. [---] o proco (n) s (uli) c (larissimo) · v (iro)
3. [---] i optimo

Apparatus

Text from autopsy (Prag)

Translation

Commentary

The text is an honorific for an individual of proconsular rank, since the titles proconsul and clarissimus vir and the epithet optimo all appear in the dative. The curve of a letter is visible at the end of line 1 on the break (not noted by the original editor) and while this could in theory be a C, in context it must be an O (as Manganaro noted). Since there is space for no more than one more letter at the edge of the stone, this is presumably the end of a name in -idius, followed by a blank space. The traces at the start of line 3 cannot be resolved with certainty; Manganaro suggested [Halaes]ini, as those responsible for the honorific, although such a phrase might be expected at the end of the text and the ethnic in the genitive plural (after e.g. res publica or similar). Manganaro also plausibly suggested that optimo was followed in the next line by civi ac patrono, i.e. 'excellent citizen and patron', which would make the honorand a citizen of Halaesa who had achieved high imperial office. As Scibona observed, the form of the letters (and the use of the term clarissimus vir) place this text in the third (or fourth) century.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175725

EDR 075547

EDCS 9401431

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1973.0274

Scibona, G. 1971. Epigraphica Halaesina I. *Kokalos*. 17: 3-20. At 20 no.10 fig.3

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 88 no.37 n.490

Facella, A. 2006. Alesa Arconidea: ricerche su un'antica città della Sicilia tirrenica. Pisa. At 294

Scibona, G. 2008. The Epigraphs. In Scibona, G., Tigano, G.(eds.), *Alesa Archonidea. Guide to the Antiquarium*. Palermo. pp. 25-27. At 27 ph

Prestianni Giallombardo, A. M. 2012. Spazio pubblico e memoria civica. Le epigrafi dall'agora di Alesa. In Ampolo, C.(eds.), *Agora greca e agorai di Sicilia*. Pisa. pp. 171-200. At 184 fig.178

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.33

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